

MONITORING - AS A TOOL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF ADVANCED TRAINING OF PEDAGOGICAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the disclosure of the fundamentals of monitoring as a tool for increasing the effectiveness of advanced training of teaching staff in the vocational education system. The article examines the issues of monitoring the effectiveness of advanced training of teaching staff and substantiates the relationship between monitoring and improving the effectiveness of the educational process.*

Keywords: *monitoring, education, advanced training, effectiveness of advanced training, pedagogical monitoring, development strategy, information, monitoring study.*

Introduction

On the basis of the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (№-UP-5847 dated 8.10.2019), the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (№3PY-637 dated 24.09.2020) and a number of programs and strategies aimed at the development of the education system as a whole (Strategies for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026 (№UP-60 dated 28.01.2022), Strategy "Uzbekistan-2030" (№UP-158 of 11.09.2023) and other targeted programs for the development of education), key directions of improving the efficiency of educational institutions are highlighted. Among them, special attention is paid to ensuring a high level of quality and efficiency of education and creating conditions for its accessibility.

Monitoring the effectiveness of education is recognized as one of the most important tools for achieving these goals and objectives. It involves the development of clear criteria and methods for assessing the educational process, the organization of regular monitoring of the results of training, education and personal growth of students, the collection of reliable information on the course of the educational process and compliance with its state requirements and the demands of modern society. Modern trends in updating the content of education, the introduction of innovative methods and a variety of forms of educational organizations make the modernization of the process of control and pedagogical research relevant. Thus, the task of building a system for monitoring the improvement of the effectiveness of education becomes a central problem in the management of the modern system of vocational education. This aspect becomes especially important in the light of the development of modern training approaches, characterized by a focus on the formation of competencies and the implementation of an activity approach in training. Achieving compliance with the new requirements requires the introduction of appropriate evaluation criteria and effective measurement procedures.

As we noted above, in the modern world the importance of education is growing as the most important factor in the formation of a new quality not only of the economy, but also of society as a whole. Education is becoming an area of activity open to society, which is necessary to

improve the quality of human capital. Today, obtaining high-quality education largely determines the demand for a specialist in the labor market, his competitiveness in rapidly changing socio-economic conditions. Ultimately, the quality of education is crucial for building a personal professional development trajectory of a specialist. Only an independent and creative professional, an active subject in the educational services market, having an individual style of professional activity, able to manage his intellectual potential, constantly developing his pedagogical competence, capable of implementing modern ideas.

Thus, the urgent issue today is to improve the educational and professional level of teachers and evaluate its results with the help of monitoring research. In professional pedagogy, some system-forming elements of monitoring were reflected in the works of Bespalko V.P., Golish L.V., Akhmetova K.I., Mayorova A.N., Silina S.N., Simonov V.P. [1-5] and other authors. The study found that the achievement of the quality of the advanced training process is inextricably linked with the development and implementation of monitoring of its results. Based on the existing research in the field of monitoring theory and methodology, taking into account different interpretations of the concepts of "monitoring" and "monitoring the effectiveness of the advanced training process", we have formulated their working definitions.

Monitoring of the education system is a systematic standardized observation of the state of education and the dynamics of changes in its results, the conditions for the implementation of educational activities, the contingent of students, the educational and extracurricular achievements of students, the professional achievements of graduates of organizations engaged in educational activities, the state of the network of organizations carrying out educational activities. Monitoring is carried out for the purpose of information support for the development and implementation of the state policy of Uzbekistan in the field of education, continuous systematic analysis and assessment of the state and prospects for the development of education (including in terms of the effectiveness of the activities of organizations engaged in educational activities), strengthening the effectiveness of the functioning of the educational system by improving the quality of management decisions made for it, as well as in order to identify violations of the requirements of the legislation on education.

Monitoring the effectiveness of education is a system of collecting, processing, storing and disseminating information on the activities of the education system, as well as on the satisfaction of internal and external consumers of educational services. Based on this, we can accurately assert that monitoring the effectiveness of advanced training of pedagogical personnel is a scientifically based method of continuous, control and evaluation, diagnostic and prognostic tracking of the progress of the process of advanced training and trends in its development. Its purpose is a strictly time-defined assessment and fixation of the quality of the advanced training process, carried out in comparison with the regulatory parameters of state requirements by means of special tools.

The substantive side of monitoring the effectiveness of advanced training of pedagogical personnel can be represented in two aspects:

- firstly, as the content of research activities at different stages of monitoring: definition of the goals of tracking advanced training of teachers; analysis of the content of advanced training programs; definition of criteria, indicators, indicators, methods of assessing the formation of demanded competence, as well as pedagogical conditions affecting its formation; design of the research situation; implementation of research results into practice; parallel conduct of longitudinal studies; adjustment of the content of advanced training and setting goals for the implementation of new development vectors;

• secondly, as the content of pedagogical and managerial conditions implemented in the course of advanced training. These conditions include: theoretical module of advanced training, practical module, technical and technological content of advanced training and scientific and methodological support of educational activities. It should be noted that the actual implementation of the theoretical and practical modules of advanced training can be carried out during the implementation of the invariant and variational part of the modular advanced training program on courses in the advanced training system.

The substantive aspect of monitoring determines the specific structure of the information field: the object of study, the levels of the object's study, the subject of monitoring, sources of information, methods of monitoring research, means and technologies of monitoring research, forms of providing results and management decision. The procedural side of monitoring the quality of advanced training of pedagogical personnel is presented:

- in actions at each stage of monitoring;
- in actions related to the construction of modules, tools, technologies for the implementation of pedagogical conditions.

It is the structuring of information and timely analysis of the dynamics and state of the educational process at advanced training courses that allow to ensure its quality and thereby improve the quality of professional training of pedagogical personnel. So, monitoring, in essence, is a special phenomenon, it is multidimensional, continuous, objective, integrative. In our opinion, monitoring studies of the quality of the advanced training process perform the following functions:

- informational - regular in accordance with the program and schedule of tracking the progress (results) of the advanced training process on the basis of their constant recording, evaluation and compliance with the specified criteria;

- organizational - targeted collection, generalization, systematization and analysis of information for making decisions on the optimal choice of educational goals and means of their solution or correction of the tasks performed, or forecasting trends in the development of the system of advanced training;

- control and evaluation - operational control and evaluation of the effectiveness of the pedagogical actions carried out and the completeness of the implementation of the ultimate goals of the system of advanced training of pedagogical personnel;

• training - disclosure of the causes of shortcomings in pedagogical work, identification of specific ways and means of ensuring the quality of the process of advanced training; teach teachers a deep understanding of the tasks facing them, the ability to persistently and consistently implement them in practice, deeply analyze and self-critically evaluate its results;

- developmental - broadening the horizons of teachers, the growth of general culture, the development of intellectual, moral qualities.

• correctional - prompt search and clarification of the reasons for the current situation and, if necessary, correction of the tasks performed;

• diagnostic and prognostic - timely identification of changes occurring in the process of advanced training, in particular in the system of advanced training of pedagogical personnel, in general, making a pedagogical diagnosis, establishing cause-and-effect relationships and prompt forecasting of their further development.

In the procedural aspect, the implementation of these functions is carried out operationally, that is, through the sequential execution of "monitoring operations" that form a certain algorithm. We present it schematically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Pedagogical monitoring algorithm

Based on the conducted research, we will set out our own interpretation of the key concepts of the study and formulate their working definitions. In our understanding, "monitoring" is a multidimensional, integral and systemic concept. Pedagogical monitoring implies long-term and systematic, scientifically based, specially organized observation and tracking of trends in the system and in the object of advanced training itself in order to obtain information for comparing them with a given standard, their control, evaluation, and forecast, as well as management decision-making.

The effectiveness of the advanced training process is determined by the fact that its results must comply with the goals of advanced training and the final result set by the regulatory documents. Monitoring the effectiveness of the advanced training process is a scientifically based method of continuous, control and evaluation, diagnostic and prognostic monitoring of the progress of the advanced training process and trends in its development. Its purpose is a strictly time-defined assessment and recording of the effectiveness of the advanced training process, carried out in comparison with the regulatory parameters of state requirements by means of special tools. Monitoring and evaluation technology is an orderly set of optimal methods and means of pedagogical monitoring that instrumentally ensure the implementation of the goal of monitoring and the achievement of certain results in these conditions for making managerial and pedagogical decisions. Monitoring the effectiveness of the advanced training process performs the following functions:

- informational - regular in accordance with the program and schedule of tracking the progress (results) of the advanced training process on the basis of their constant recording, evaluation and compliance with the specified criteria;
- organizational - targeted collection, generalization, systematization and analysis of information for making decisions on the optimal choice of educational goals and means of their solution or correction of the tasks performed, or forecasting trends in the development of the system of advanced training;
- control and evaluation - operational control and evaluation of the effectiveness of the pedagogical actions carried out and the completeness of the implementation of the final goals of the system of advanced training of pedagogical personnel of the SSPO;
- educational - disclosure of the causes of shortcomings in pedagogical work, outline of specific ways and means of ensuring the effectiveness of the process of advanced training; teach teachers a deep understanding of the tasks facing them, the ability to persistently and consistently implement them in practice, deeply analyze and self-critically evaluate its results;

- developmental - broadening the horizons of teachers, the growth of general culture, the development of intellectual, moral qualities.

- correctional - prompt search and clarification of the reasons for the current situation and, if necessary, correction of the tasks performed;

- diagnostic and prognostic - timely identification of changes occurring in the process of advanced training, in particular in the system of advanced training of pedagogical personnel of the SSPO, in general, making a pedagogical diagnosis, establishing causal relationships and promptly forecasting their further development.

Successful achievement of the goal and solution of tasks within an educational institution are possible only if the principles of monitoring organization are implemented. Let's briefly consider their essence. Purposefulness - consists in the exact choice of the purpose of monitoring, in order to direct all the work on monitoring the process of advanced training to solve the main tasks facing the staff of the educational institution and to have an effective impact on its activities.

Comprehensiveness - involves the coverage of all aspects of educational work, all areas of the advanced training process, all categories of pedagogical personnel. Objectivity is the determination of the real state of the advanced training system, the exact picture of pedagogical phenomena, their fundamental assessment. Systematic - means a constant, systematic, logically consistent study of the state of the process of advanced training, the work of teachers and students throughout the process of advanced training (one month), allowing to track the growth of pedagogical skills of teachers, improving the effectiveness of the process of advanced training and knowledge of students.

Effectiveness is its effectiveness, efficiency, timely adoption of management and pedagogical decisions during monitoring and based on its results, prompt implementation of these decisions. Effectiveness - is achieved by an in-depth analysis of the identified shortcomings, objective conclusions, constructive proposals, thoughtful follow-up work aimed at correcting the shortcomings. Publicity is one of the important measures of public influence. Monitoring is carried out openly. The terms and objects of monitoring, as well as the objectives of monitoring, are announced in advance. All its subjects participate in the discussion of the monitoring results: both inspectors, experts, listeners, and those teachers whose work is analyzed.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be argued that all functions and principles of monitoring are subordinated to one common goal - to improve the effectiveness of the process of advanced training of pedagogical personnel and are aimed at providing a scientific approach in the management of the educational process.

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